

NEUROURBANISM AND ACCESSIBLE TOURISM: SAVORING DESIGN AS A THERAPEUTIC PROPOSAL FOR HEALTHY AGING

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ABSTRACT: *It's estimated that by 2100, the population aged 60 or over will reach 30% in the world, according to UN data from 2024. It's also expected that the vast majority of elderly people will live in urban environments, especially in low- and middle-income countries, such as Brazil, Africa and Asian countries. In this perspective, this study aims to investigate how NeuroUrbanism and Environmental Gerontology can contribute to the creation of accessible and therapeutic tourist environments for the elderly, proposing the concept of "savoring design" as an approach to improve the well-being of older tourists. As an exploratory method, an integrative literature review was adopted, covering research published between 2018 and 2024 on urban accessibility, healthy aging and tourism. The analysis revealed that urban environments designed based on the principles of NeuroUrbanism can reduce stress, improve safety and encourage social interactions among the elderly. Savoring design, inspired by Positive Psychology, was highlighted as an effective approach to promoting conscious appreciation of the environment through aesthetic landscapes, green areas, rest areas and accessible pathways, thus improving relaxation and quality of life for older adults during their tourism experiences. The results indicate that, in addition to meeting the physical needs of accessibility and safety, urban planning should integrate interventions that promote the emotional and cognitive well-being of older tourists. The conclusion suggests that accessible urban design, combined with strategies that promote well-being, is essential to ensure that tourist destinations are inclusive and welcoming.*

KEYWORDS: *urbanism; tourism; neuroscience; accessibility; healthy aging.*

INTRODUCTION

By 2100, 1 in 3 people will be 60 years of age or older worldwide (UN, 2024). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the proportion of people aged 60 or older is expected to double between 2020 and 2050, rising from 12% to around 22%. This equates to more than 2 billion people aged 60 or older worldwide by mid-century (PAHO, 2020). According to projections from the UN Population Division, between 1950 and 2100, the age group of elderly people aged 60 and over is expected to grow 15.4 times in the period, which has been characterized as a profound process of population aging (UN, 2024). In addition to the

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issue of increased life expectancy, the United Nations Human Settlements Program (UN-HABITAT) showed that 55% of the world's population lived in urban areas in 2021, rising to 68% by 2050 (UN, 2022). It is estimated that 79% of the population of Latin America and Caribbean lives in large urban centers. Therefore, it is expected that the vast majority of older people will live in urban environments, especially in low- and middle-income countries, such as Brazil, Africa and Asian countries (UN, 2022).

Aging is characterized by physiological changes, such as modifications to physical and sensory capacity, as well as cognitive and emotional changes. However, such changes do not occur uniformly in all individuals (Batistoni *et al.*, 2014). Heterogeneity in aging is marked by differences in health trajectories, lifestyles, socioeconomic status, and environmental context (Freitas and Py, 2022). A cross-sectional study involving more than 3,100 elderly individuals aged 60 or over found that residents living in socioeconomically advantaged neighborhoods with access to parks and public squares have greater cognitive reserve¹ than populations who aged in neighborhoods far from urban centers, with little or no presence of green areas effectively accessible to the community (Soloveva *et al.*, 2023). Recognizing the importance of healthy aging and the implications of this process on the population, the UN General Assembly and WHO declared the “Decade of Healthy Aging (2021-2030)”. The aim is to unite governments, international organizations, health professionals, civil society and other stakeholders to improve the lives of older people, their families and communities (PAHO, 2020).

Accessible Tourism (AT) is a field that is increasingly developing, with the central objective of removing physical, sensory and attitudinal barriers, allowing people with disabilities, reduced mobility and other conditions to have full access to tourist experiences. Initially focused on the inclusion of people with disabilities (PWDs), AT has evolved to encompass the concept of Universal Design (UD), created in the 1960s by Ronald Lawrence Mace, whose premise is tourism projects for all age groups and conditions, ensuring equal access (Speck, Di Marco and Natividade, 2016). Even with around 1 billion inhabitants in the world with some type of physical or intellectual disability, 80% of whom live in developing countries, accessibility is not only a matter of social inclusion in the tourism sector, but also an economic opportunity (UN, 2022). In built environments, it is guided by the ISO 21902:2021 standard, entitled "Tourism and related services — Accessible tourism for all". According to

¹ *Cognitive reserve is characterized as the brain's ability to tolerate pathological changes, such as those associated with aging or neurodegenerative diseases, without presenting clinical manifestations of cognitive decline (Stern, 2009).*

the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), older people are increasingly active in the travel and tourism sector, representing a growing market (OECD, 2023). With more time available after retirement and often with financial resources, this age group in society is willing to explore new tourism experiences, as long as accessibility conditions are adequate to their needs (OECD, 2023).

In this perspective of positive emotional experiences in urban areas, Neurourbanism presents itself as an interdisciplinary field of study under construction capable of evaluating biological, psychological and social influences during population aging, taking into account not only the physical structure of the city, but also the emotionality present in individual and collective flows on a given territorial scale (Adli *et al.*, 2017; Hollander and Sussman, 2020). It aims to explore the relationship between urban environments, the human brain, cognition and mental health. Combining principles from psychiatry, urban planning, psychology, neuroscience, architecture, sociology, philosophy and ethnography, this field studies how cities and urban design influence the well-being and mental health of inhabitants (Adli *et al.*, 2017; Hollander and Sussman, 2020). The convergence of this knowledge aims to understand how urban space can affect the human brain in the short, medium and long term, investigating elements such as spatial perception, lighting, air quality, temperature, noise, among others.

METHODOLOGY

Recognizing the importance of AT in the context of social rights, inclusion and well-being in city design, this study aims to analyze how urban variables, such as lighting, air quality, thermal and acoustic comfort and the presence of green areas, directly influence the brain responses of tourists over 60 years old, taking into account knowledge from neuroscience, positive psychology and environmental gerontology. Aiming to guide design decisions in urban areas in favor of AT and, consequently, provide health and quality of life for occupants, we propose the implementation of evidence-based design (EBD)¹, capable of fostering therapeutic and memorable experiences. Therefore, as this is an exploratory study, an integrated literature review was carried out involving the keywords “neuroscience”, “accessible tourism”, “urban space” and “healthy aging”. For the review, in addition to the question “How can fully accessible urban areas provide therapeutic experiences for elderly tourists?”, the following criteria were adopted: articles published between 2018 and 2024, peer-reviewed and in English.

¹ *This method is particularly relevant in the creation of urban environments, as it seeks to maximize human well-being, health and functionality of space based on verified evidence (Ravensbergen and El-Geneidy, 2022).*

The Boolean operators used were “AND” and “OR”. Of the 1,012 initial articles, 8 were compatible with the study proposal and were therefore analyzed. Complementary authors such as Bryant and Veroff (2007), Pallasmaa (2015), Adli *et al.* (2017), Hollander and Sussman (2020), Olszewska-Guzzo (2023) among others, were of fundamental importance for understanding the theme. The aim is, therefore, to formulate evidence-based urban design proposals, taking into account the responsibility of urban planning professionals to design environments beyond technical regulations, capable of not only allowing, but providing significant, memorable and therapeutic experiences to tourists and elderly citizens, combining urban planning and tourist accessibility.

RESULTS

After analyzing the articles, the current state of the art of the proposed theme has not yet been considered in the academic scenario, especially the convergence of the theme of Neurourbanism with AT. However, from the moment the subjects are analyzed separately, AT is at the beginning of its development, essentially in the theme of integrated urban routes for the elderly in densely urbanized cities (Escuderos, Andreu and Ros, 2021). The same occurs with Neurourbanism, whose publications began in 2017 (Ndaguba *et al.*, 2022). Another important point was the growth of productions about neuroscience applied to tourism. According to Michael *et al.* (2019), neuroscience applied to tourism aims to explore the understanding of specific mental processes in human behaviors in tourist experiences, suggesting that unconscious emotional and cognitive responses are natural processes that need to be studied and understood, not as special cases, but that are incorporated as natural parts of tourism research in favor of investigations centered on users and feelings of well-being and performance quality in tourist experience spaces (Michael *et al.*, 2019).

Through EBD, the premise of “savoring design” was highlighted as an effective approach to promote conscious appreciation of the environment through aesthetic landscapes, green areas, rest areas and accessible paths, allowing sensory reconnection with nature and, consequently, qualifying the tourist experiences of the elderly population in urban spaces. Savoring experiences refer to the set of sensations, perceptions, thoughts, behaviors and emotions that an individual experiences when paying attention to and appreciating a positive stimulus or experience, influenced by both environmental characteristics and situational circumstances. The intensity and quality of these experiences vary according to duration, complexity, ability to reduce stress, self-regulation and the social interactions involved (Bryant

and Veroff, 2007). In the context of urban space, savoring can be understood as the conscious experience of pleasant sensations derived from interaction with the environment.

The integration of multisensory experience with savoring design in urban space suggests that environments should be designed to provide rich and varied stimuli that promote a tactile, auditory and olfactory perception of space (Ravensbergen and El-Geneidy, 2022). An architecture that only appeals to the sense of sight fails to fully engage the body and is therefore not capable of generating a complete and meaningful experience of space. Instead, he argues that space should be experienced through a deep and holistic interaction, in which the body becomes an instrument of perception (Pallasmaa, 2015). For older adults, who often suffer from changes in their sensory capacities, spaces that offer subtle variations in texture, temperature and sound can be therapeutic, stimulating the brain and providing enriching experiences (Freitas and Py, 2022). Considering the proposal of AT in urban areas capable of providing therapeutic, pleasant and memorable experiences for elderly tourists, the applicability of “savoring design” was investigated in an interdisciplinary manner in six variables of urban design: (i) lighting, (ii) noise pollution, (iii) air quality, (iv) presence of green areas, (v) perception of safety and (vi) urban furniture, shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Savoring Design guidelines for accessible tourism in urban environments.

Cognitive and emotional implications of spatial variable	Design Guidelines
(I) Lighting is a critical variable to ensure the safety, spatial orientation and comfort of users, especially the elderly. Studies show that lighting directly affects mood and cognition, regulating circadian rhythms and influencing the limbic system, which is responsible for emotional response. For elderly tourists, poor lighting can cause disorientation, insecurity and stress, especially at night, increasing the risk of falls and reducing the quality of the experience (Ndaguba <i>et al.</i> , 2022).	<p>Integrative Lighting: use lighting technologies that mimic natural light and adjust color temperature throughout the day to support the circadian rhythm, promoting greater cognitive and emotional well-being.</p> <p>Focus on Safety Perception: ensure uniform lighting without deep shadows to reduce the fear of accidents or crimes in urban spaces, especially in areas with high tourist concentrations and rest stops.</p> <p>Focus on Visual Cues: implement strategic lighting at points of interest and signage to facilitate navigation and reduce cognitive overload for seniors, promoting a more pleasant and safe experience.</p>
(ii) Noise pollution in cities can be detrimental to mental and cognitive health, contributing to increased stress, mental	Low Noise Pollution Zones: create rest areas where noise pollution is minimized by means of natural acoustic barriers, such as trees and shrubs,

<p>fatigue and hearing loss, especially in elderly populations. Excessive noise directly affects the prefrontal cortex and other areas responsible for attention and working memory, compromising the ability of elderly people to orient themselves and appreciate tourist environments. Creating quiet areas and pleasant sound experiences can significantly increase savoring and improve the cognitive health of elderly tourists (Ravensbergen and El-Geneidy, 2022).</p>	<p>or artificial ones, such as acoustic walls. Incorporation of Natural Sounds: promote positive auditory experiences, such as the sound of water fountains or birdsong, which can calm the nervous system and facilitate the savoring experience. Urban Noise Management: establish regulations that limit noise levels in areas with high concentrations of elderly people and tourists, especially in tourist areas of high cultural and historical value.</p>
<p>(iii) Air quality has direct implications for physical and mental health, influencing cognitive and emotional functioning. Prolonged exposure to air pollutants can cause inflammation in the brain, contributing to cognitive decline in the elderly and compromising the tourist experience. Urban environments with high air quality not only promote physical health, but also improve mental clarity and overall well-being, essential for a positive savoring experience (Grigorescu <i>et al.</i>, 2020).</p>	<p>Creating Green Corridors: integrating ecological corridors and green areas that help filter the air and reduce pollution, while also providing therapeutic spaces for walking and relaxation. Air Quality Monitoring: using real-time air quality monitoring technology and providing this information in an accessible way to tourists and residents so they can make informed decisions about their travel. Reducing Pollution Sources: implementing strategies to reduce vehicle emissions and other pollutants in tourist areas, such as promoting electric public transportation and limiting traffic in certain areas.</p>
<p>(iv) The presence of green spaces are essential for promoting mental and physical well-being, especially in densely populated urban environments. From a neuroscientific perspective, contact with nature stimulates the limbic system and other areas related to emotional processing and memory, facilitating the savoring experience. For older tourists, accessible and well-designed green spaces provide opportunities for relaxation, social interaction, and sensory stimulation that can reduce stress and improve mood (Olszewska-Guizzo, 2023).</p>	<p>Biophilic Design: incorporate natural elements, such as vegetation, water and natural light, in a coherent manner throughout the urban landscape, creating pleasant and stimulating microclimates for the brain. Accessibility in Green Areas: ensure that green areas are easily accessible by ramps and adequate paving, promoting the inclusion of people with reduced mobility and other special needs. Social Interaction Spaces: provide meeting and social spaces in parks and squares, which encourage intergenerational interaction and the formation of communities, fundamental elements for healthy aging.</p>
<p>(v) The perception of safety is a determining factor in the quality of the tourist experience, especially for the elderly, who tend to be more vulnerable to dangers and accidents. Urban safety is directly related to emotional well-being and the ability to explore the city without fear or stress. Safe spaces facilitate</p>	<p>Adequate lighting: as mentioned above, lighting plays a key role in the perception of security. Well-lit environments reduce the feeling of vulnerability and increase users’ confidence in the space. Active Surveillance and Monitoring: implement discreet surveillance systems and a visible police presence to reinforce security without</p>

<p>savoring, allowing the elderly to fully enjoy their tourist experiences (Hollander and Sussman, 2021).</p>	<p>compromising the feeling of freedom and comfort. Preventative Design: propose urban spaces that discourage criminal behavior through design strategies that increase visibility and constant occupancy of public spaces.</p>
<p>(vi) Urban furniture is considered a key component for the comfort and functionality of public spaces. For older people, the availability of comfortable and accessible seating at strategic points can significantly improve the tourist experience, allowing them to rest, socialize and absorb the environment more efficiently. In addition, the ergonomics and suitability of urban furniture can directly influence savoring, promoting a longer and more enjoyable experience (Michael <i>et al.</i>, 2019).</p>	<p>Functional and Comfortable Furniture: design benches and seats that provide ergonomic support and are located in areas that allow for the enjoyment of scenic views or social events, promoting savoring. Diversifying Furniture Types: offer a variety of furniture options, including backless and backless seating, picnic tables, and lounge chairs, to accommodate the different needs and preferences of senior tourists. Accessible Furniture: ensure that all street furniture is accessible to people with reduced mobility, including raised seating options, armrests, and non-slip surfaces.</p>

DISCUSSION

Implementing the concept of savoring design in cities requires a systematic and integrated approach that considers urban, tourism, and strategic planning needs. Cities such as Copenhagen and Singapore have adopted successful practices that integrate efficient public transport infrastructure with tourist zones and green areas, promoting inclusive mobility (OECD, 2023). Interconnectivity between tourist hotspots and the use of accessible transportation, such as subways, buses, and bike paths, significantly improves the mobility experience of older adults who require physical or cognitive support (Grigorescu *et al.*, 2020). New York City’s High Line is a significant example of how urban planning interventions can transform urban areas into spaces for enriching sensory and aesthetic experiences, aligning with the principles of savoring design and inclusive urbanism. The project provides a walkable and connected environment, while integrating variables such as vegetation, strategic lighting, and adapted street furniture (Ravensbergen and El-Geneidy, 2022).

By connecting tourist areas with transportation modes and ensuring that urban planning addresses accessibility needs, cities can provide an inclusive and enriching tourist experience for all users (Escuderos, Andreu and Ros, 2021). The integration of green spaces, the installation of urban furniture that allows for relaxation and contemplation, and the control of urban lighting and sound are essential to creating environments that encourage savoring and promote the mental health and well-being of residents and tourists. Ultimately, savoring design

has the potential to transform the urban experience, especially for older adults, promoting health, well-being, and memorable experiences in densely urbanized cities.

CONCLUSIONS

These guidelines, informed by the principles of neuroscience, gerontology and accessible tourism, have the potential to profoundly reconfigure the urban tourism experience aimed at senior citizens, promoting the creation of more welcoming, safe and cognitively stimulating environments. By emphasizing key variables such as adequate lighting, harmonious soundscapes, air quality, presence of green areas, improved security and ergonomic arrangement of street furniture, planners can structure spaces that encourage the practice of savoring. This allows senior tourists, when interacting with such environments, to experience more intense and pleasurable experiences, resulting in cognitive and emotional gains. The process of healthy aging transcends medical care and individual behaviors, proving to be equally dependent on the configuration of the urban environment, which should be designed to stimulate brain function through enriching sensory, social and emotional experiences. By incorporating these guidelines into city planning, it is possible to not only attract a greater number of senior tourists, but also ensure that their experiences are marked by positive and lasting memories, while providing conditions for healthy aging of residents.

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